

Fracture of Mandible : A Review of Literature

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Abstract

Fracture of mandible accounts for 25% out of all maxillofacial fractures. Most common cause is vehicular accidents, assaults, falls and then sports activities. The body fractures are mainly classified into 2 types i.e., favourable and unfavourable fractures on the basis of fracture line and the effect of muscle pull. Evaluation can be done via OPG Xray, CT scan, etc. There are two methods to treat mandibular fracture i.e., surgical management (open reduction) and non surgical management (closed reduction). Most common complications of mandibular body fractures are osteomyelitis or infection.

Introduction

Out of all maxillofacial fractures, the 25% are fracture of mandible.^[1] Mandible body fractures accounts for almost 11%-36%, with personal violence as the principal factor among the different types mandible fracture.^[2]

Etiology

The etiology of mandible body fractures are violence/assault, falls, sports activities and vehicular accidents.^{[2][1]} Most common cause is vehicular accidents that is 43%, followed by assault that is 34%, then falls (7%) and sports accidents that is 4%.

Epidemiology

According the various studies in all the mandibular fractures, the mandible body fracture is 29% (11-36% range), followed by condyle and angle. Condylar and body fractures are most prevalent maxillofacial fractures in children.^[3] Body fractures are more common in males than females.^[1]

Pathophysiology

Fracture of mandible body generally occurs between the distal aspect of canine and a hypothetical line that communicate to the region of anterior attachment of the masseter muscle. They are classified based on the position of teeth relative to the fracture, anatomic location, favourableness and the direction of fracture line.^{[4][5]}

Based on the direction of fracture line and the effect of muscle distraction on the fracture fragments, the body fractures are classified into two types ; favourable and unfavourable fractures. The body fragments are drawn together by muscle distraction in favourable fracture but the body fragments becomes displaced by the muscle forces is unfavourable fractures.

There are various muscles which exerted forces that furnish unfavourable fractures are medial pterygoid muscle, masseter and temporalis. The muscles deflect the proximal bony segments in the supermedial direction. Moreover, mylohyoid and anterior belly of diaphragm may also plays a role in displacing the segment in the posterior and inferior direction.

History and Physical Examination

History

Patient's thorough history include any collagen vascular disorder, neoplasia affecting the bone, pre-existing systemic bone disease, arthritis and temporomandibular joint dysfunction must merit consideration. Any additional fractures preserve and the

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nature of the injury is the assessable traumatic force. Vehicular accidents tends to have a larger magnitude forces which results in multiple, compound, comminuted mandibular fractures compared to assaults that results in a single , simple, non displaced fractures.

Physical Examination

Intraorally, on physical examination a change in occlusion may be apparent. Anaesthesia, paresthesia or dysesthesia of the lower lip may be present. Sensation of lower lip changes generally in displaced body fractures that are distal to mandibular foramen (along with the distribution of the inferior alveolar nerve) and they are not generally seen in non displaced mandibular fractures.^{[6][7]}

In general, the common sign of body fractures are step defects in the occlusion, laceration in the gingiva , and/or ecchymosis in the floor of the mouth. Mobility in the fractures should be noted by the examiner by the use of both hands on the occlusal surface of the teeth and finger on the inferior border of the mandible. Then slowly carefully, pressure should be between the two hands.^{[6][7]}

Extraorally, there may be change in facial contour due to skin abrasion and loss of external mandibular form. Flattened appearance of the lateral aspect of the face often results due to body fracture. Loss of the mandibular body present on palpation. An unfavourable fractures should be suspected. Anterior face may get displaced in the forward direction which results in the elongation. In these cases, the anterior mandible displaced in the downward direction. Other finding include hematoma, ecchymosis and laceration.

Evaluation

Evaluation of the body fractures is done via radiographs using plain radiography (occlusal, lateral -oblique, panoramic, peri-apical and posteroanterior views) and CT Scan. Caldwell posteroanterior view shows the presence of the medial or lateral displacement of body fractures. The lateral oblique view helps to diagnose posterior body fractures. Panoramic radiographic is the most informative among all the radiographs. Entire mandible can be viewed in a single plain along with several advantages such as cost effectiveness, simplicity of technique and low radiation exposure compared with CT or CBCT (Cone Beam Computed Tomography) . In severely traumatised patient it is challenging to take a panoramic radiograph because it usually requires the patient to be upright postion. Also, it becomes difficult to appreciate buccolingual bone displacement as it is a 2-D image.

CBCT can be useful as it is highly sensitive in identifying fractures when convention 2-D radiographs cannot give accurate picture of the fracture. Also, it decreases the chances of interpretation error and provides better image quality.^{[7][8]}

Treatment/Management

There are 2 methods to treat mandibular fracture i.e., surgical management and non -surgical conservative management. The treatment of fractures using non-surgical or surgical means depending on the type , consequences and severity of fracture. In

non surgical management (also known as closed reduction), MMF (maxillomandibular fixation) serves to stabilise the fracture.^[9]

It offers various advantages such as it is a less invasive procedure, low sensitivity to the professional experience and low cost as it does not requires any surgical treatment and hospitalisation. However MMF should not occur in a patient with seizure disorder, intellectual disability, pregnancy, multiple system injuries, psychosis , severe pulmonary dysfunction and non-complaint patient. Indication for closed reduction includes:

1. Edentulous fractures.
2. Presence of adequate occlusion.
3. Non displaced favourable fractures.
4. Grossly comminuted fractures.
5. Fractures in children with developing dentition.
6. Presence of healthy dentition with sufficient teeth to obtain a stable occlusion.
7. Good facial esthetics and adequate open mouth.

In this procedure use 24 gauge wire for the placement of Ivy Loops between 2 stable teeth followed by a smaller gauge to provide MMF between the loops (Ivy loops) frequently used arch bars are bars with 24 and 26 gauge wires. Arch bar by tension bonding mechanism provides additional stability which results in a second line of resistance. While placing arch bars , at least includes all the teeth in the affected quadrant of the mandible. It is not necessary to enclose whole dental arch . Arch bars have low cost, are easy to place , reduce the distraction of the bones at the healing site and restore normal occlusion. However, they provide only semirigid fixation and requires a second procedure for their removal. By using circum mandibular wires dentures can be wired to the jaw in the case of an edentulous mandible. Due to wires in the mandibular vestibule postoperative discomfort present. Also , there is a risk of damage to structures on the floor of mouth and there is a risk of submental scar formation.^[10]

MMF screws are an alternative option to fix the dentures. These are self tapping screws, that placed in the sound bone in the vestibular regions anteriorly and posteriorly. They provide a bone anchor where wires or elastics can be placed for MMF while establishing the occlusion of patients.^{[11][12]} By placing arch bars in the denture and intermaxillary fixation can be achieved. In such cases another options are Gunning Splints.^[13]

In surgical management i.e., internal rigid fixation (IRF) and open reduction, the fracture site easily visualise by surgeon and control the reduction. There is the quick recovery of the occlusion, maintainance of periodontal tissue, reconstruction of anatomic osseous morphology to its pre-surgery form , and due to good nutrition and verbal communication return to early function.^[14] However, there is a risk of increased morbidity in it. A tooth in line of fracture may need to extract before any surgical treatment. Extraction is indicated when the tooth has compromised periodontium resulting in mobility or has fracture roots, or has an extensive peri apical infection or it is impossible or

difficult to reduce the fracture due to the presence of the tooth. However, that tooth may help in guiding the reduction of fracture before extracting. After applying for the plate across the fracture, the occlusion is checked and the reduction is confirmed. The screws and plates are then removed, extraction of tooth is done and the plate reapplied by replacing the screws in the initial holes.

Surgical management can be take place using and extraoral or intraoral approach, the choice depends mainly on the type of body fracture and on the site. Preferably treatment for simple and fracture in the entire segment with no or slight dislocation by use of intraoral approach.^[15] The intraoral approach provides great access to the fracture site and it allows observing of the occlusion to reduce fracture and application of rigid fixation. Approximately 5 to 7 mm incision is placed in the vestibular region below the mucogingival junction to facilitate closure. The location also helps in the prevention of wound dehiscence. Care is necessary to avoid injuring the mental nerve during an intraoral approach.

On the other hand, the clinician can treat fracture in the posterior segment with a high degree of dislocation and comminuted fracture with an extraoral approach as placing stronger and longer plates is difficult by intraoral approach. Fracture that lie between the mandibular body inferior and lingual aspects extraoral surgical approach may be use. To avoid injury in the marginal mandibular nerve care should be done.^{[16][17]}

Indication for Open Reduction

1. Fracture of an edentulous mandible (involving a severe displacement of fracture fragments) to re establish mandible continuity.
2. Displaced unfavourable body fracture.

Postoperatively, analgesics should be given to the patient with open reduction, to cover gram positive organisms antibiotic therapy should be given. Nutritional needs reevaluation should also follows. Inter maxillary fixation (IMF) is maintained for 4 to 6 weeks in most of the adult mandibular fracture cases. 2 weeks may sufficient for patients with a minimal displaced fracture in the tooth bearing area. A radiograph should be done to ensure the union of the fracture after the removal of wires.

Differential Diagnosis

Thorough evaluation and monitoring of the patient's general physical condition are necessary before treating mandibular body fracture. Force which cause mandibular body fracture may also injures other organs system. There may occur pneumothorax, pneumomediastinum, concurrent postraumatic thrombosis occlusion of the internal carotid artery posterior basilar skull fracture, spleen laceration and bilateral cervical subcutaneous emphysema after trauma. Therefore, patients should not treated unless there issues are addressed by surgical reduction of mandibular body fractures.

Prognosis

Favourable results in terms of bony union can be achieved by both open and closed reduction of mandibular body fractures. As the fractured teeth may become infected and jeopardise the

treatment of dental injuries should be done concurrently with the fracture. Hence, they require removal. Mandibular canines should be preserved as it help to determine the occlusion, if possible. Edentulous body fractures the management and prognosis are often challenging due to multiple comorbidities and advanced age.

Complications

Most common complication is osteomyelitis or infection (resulting in malunion or non-union). Contributing factors are:^[18]

1. Alcohol abuse and Chronic disease.
2. Oral Sepsis.
3. Fracture of the plate.
4. Poor patient compliance.
5. Displacement of fracture.
6. The prolonged time prior to treatment.
7. Teeth in the fracture line.

Other complications are delayed union of the fractured mandible. The airway may get impaired if the mandible body fraction is bilateral along with the parasymphseal, or condylar fractures. This impairment resulting in the obstruction of the oropharynx by the tongue because of the muscular action that pulls the distal mandibular segment backward. There may also nerve damage such as neurotmesis, in which function may take around 18 months to return or neuropraxia, in which function takes around 4-6 weeks to return.

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